

Ecliptic pole scanning in the astrometric solution

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Abstract

The astrometric accuracy of Gaia at a given time in the mission is evaluated for different durations of the ecliptic pole scanning.

Document History

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1 Introduction

The particular pattern in which Gaia scans the celestial sphere, known as the Nominal Scanning Law (NSL, Fig. 1), is carefully designed to optimize the astrometric accuracy, sky coverage and uniformity within given technical constraints, in particular a constant solar aspect angle $\xi = 45^\circ$ and an upper limit on the across-scan speed of stellar images. The rationale for the NSL is elaborated in Lindegren (SAG-LL-014) and Lindegren & Bastian (2011). The optimisation means that any deviation from NSL is likely to have negative effects in terms of greater non-uniformity of the sky coverage and a global increase in the astrometric uncertainties (while the results may of course improve locally). In the NSL the solar aspect angle ξ between the sun and the instrument z (\simeq spin) axis remains constant while the spin axis moves relative to the stars at the maximum across-scan speed (about 4° day^{-1}), causing the heliotropic phase angle ν (Fig. 1) to increase (or decrease) monotonically with time. The period of $\nu(t)$ is approximately 63 days.

The Ecliptic Pole Scanning Law (EPSL) was introduced in Bastian et al. (GAIA-ARI-BAS-008) in order to improve the possibilities for early high-precision calibration and high-precision astrometric performance verification during the commissioning phase. In EPSL the angle ν stays constant at either 0° (i.e., with the spin axis preceding the sun on the ecliptic) or 180° (following the sun). This means that the fields of view scan through the south and north ecliptic poles in every spin, and that the direction of scanning changes by the same rate as the sun (and spin axis) moves along the ecliptic, or about 1° day^{-1} . The main advantages of the EPSL for the initial calibration and performance verification is that a relatively small set of objects near the ecliptic poles are observed many times in a short period of time (essentially twice per spin period), and that the maximum across-scan rate is about four times smaller than in NSL. The EPSL has subsequently been adopted as a means to simplify a number of activities during commissioning (EADS Astrium, GAIA.ASF.PLN.SAT.00086), and some valid science data will probably be acquired in this mode already during commissioning. Moreover, at the end of the in-orbit commissioning phase, Gaia will probably be handed over in EPSL mode, and the scientific operations may continue in that mode for some further time in order to ease/accelerate the initial photometric calibrations (Bastian, BAS-035).

Based on purely geometric arguments it is easily seen that the EPSL is unfavourable for the resolution of the five astrometric parameters in all other parts of the sky than the ecliptic poles. For example, near the ecliptic the scans are always parallel to each other, viz., perpendicular to the ecliptic. This is fine for the determination of ecliptic latitude but not at all for the longitude, since it is almost only the along-scan measurements that matter for the astrometry (Lindegren & Bastian, 2011). Furthermore, the parallactic displacements of sources close to the ecliptic are perpendicular to the scans, making it impossible to determine their parallaxes from the along-scan measurements. Thus, for these sources there is at least a two-fold degeneracy in the geometry of the observations when trying to solve the astrometric parameters. While it is therefore desirable to switch to NSL as soon as possible, it is still true that very accurate measurements are accumulated in EPSL mode, albeit only in specific directions, and it is con-

FIGURE 1: Illustration of the Nominal Scanning Law (NSL) of Gaia, showing the path of the spin (z) axis during 4 days, and the corresponding path of the preceding viewing directions. For clarity, the path of the following viewing direction is not shown.

ceivable that these measurements could benefit the astrometric solution when combined with the NSL measurements obtained later.

There is a non-trivial trade-off between the two conflicting requirements: to extend the EPSL phase for rapid calibrations, and to start the NSL as soon as possible for acquiring astrometric data under optimal geometric conditions. This note addresses one part of the trade-off by quantifying the astrometric loss due to the EPSL in terms of the weight of the positions, parallaxes, and proper motions obtained after a certain length of the science data acquisition. More precisely, we consider E months of EPSL followed by N months of NSL, and plot the results versus the total length $L = E + N$. In this way the effects of different E at a certain point L in the mission can easily be compared. For this study it has been necessary to make a number of simplifying assumptions, which are described in the next section. Their implications for the conclusions are further addressed in the final section. Some details of the calculations are put in the Appendix.

2 Simulations

2.1 Simplifications

The statistical uncertainties of the astrometric parameters of single stars, resulting from a global astrometric solution (AGIS), include contributions of many different kinds: the centroiding errors of the individual CCD observations (which include photon-statistical noise plus read-out noise, CTI effects, etc.), modelling errors in the attitude representation and instrument geometry, and the statistical uncertainty of the fitted attitude and calibration models due to the observation noise. The accuracies of the attitude and calibration fits depend crucially on the number, spatial distribution and magnitude of suitable sources available on the sky, and actually used in the astrometric solution, as well as on the length and frequency of data gaps. It is possible (but has not been done) to take these many circumstances into account in a reasonably realistic simulation of the data and of the subsequent astrometric solution, and to analyse the statistics of the resulting errors. However, such a simulation would necessarily include a very large number of sources – at least some tens of millions –, making it utterly infeasible for parametric studies such as a comparison of different scanning laws.

Fortunately, there is a very simple way to estimate a *lower bound* to the uncertainties (or more generally the covariance) of the astrometric parameters for any given source. This is achieved basically by ignoring possible modelling errors and the statistical uncertainties of the attitude and calibration parameters. Thus, the CCD centroiding errors (assumed to be uncorrelated) are just propagated to the astrometric parameters from the known geometry of the various scans across the source. A great advantage is that this error propagation can be done separately for each source, as there is no need to consider the coupling of different sources resulting from the joint solution of attitude and calibration parameters. Moreover, if every CCD observation of a given source is assumed to have the same uncertainty σ_{AL} (not unreasonable for a non-variable star), the resulting astrometric uncertainties scale with σ_{AL} , where the scaling factors depend only on the number, times and orientations of the CCD scans across the object. When comparing different scanning laws, there is consequently no need to consider different magnitudes, and a fixed value of σ_{AL} may be used without loss of generality. Nearly all parametric optimisation studies of Gaia, as well as the accuracy analysis for the projected scientific performance of Gaia, use this highly simplified analysis, only slightly improved by including various statistical corrections for the attitude and calibration errors, and an overall error margin to take into account non-modelled effects (de Bruijne, Gaia-JdB-020). Heuristically, the approach is motivated by the design of Gaia being driven by specification goals that are always related to the theoretical, photon-limited performance. For example, specifications for the high-frequency attitude noise are set in such a way that, for most observations, attitude modelling errors will be quite small compared to the photon noise. Thus, the overall error budget is dominated by the individual CCD centroiding errors, which are well accounted for by the simplified model.

2.2 Scanning laws

The simulations use the analytical scanning laws implemented by the `EpslAndNsl` class in `GaiaTools`. In this class, the EPSL model is used for $t \leq t_{\text{switch}}$ and the NSL according to Mignard (FM-037) for $t \geq t_{\text{switch}}$, where t_{switch} is the switch-over time. The mission is assumed to start at $t_{\text{beg}} = \text{J2014.0}$, and with E months of EPSL we have $t_{\text{switch}} = t_{\text{beg}} + E$. Continuity at the switch-over point is guaranteed by letting the reference parameters for both EPSL and NSL (in particular the reference values of the angle ν and the spin phase Ω) refer to the epoch t_{switch} . By default, the preceding mode is used in EPSL, i.e., the spin axis precedes the sun on the ecliptic, or $\nu = 0$. The NSL then also starts with $\nu(t_{\text{switch}}) = 0$. The spin phase (Ω) is also continuous at t_{switch} since the the same reference value $\Omega(t_{\text{switch}}) = 0$ is used for both EPSL and NSL. We consider EPSL lengths of $E = 0, 1, \dots, 6$ months¹ and total lengths L from 6 to 60 months. A month is taken to be exactly 1/12th of a Julian year.

The use of J2014.0 as the starting date is no restriction for the present analysis. Since only a uniform distribution of sources on the celestial sphere is considered (Sect. 2.3), the phasing of the scanning law with respect to the Galactic plane is of no consequence. For the same reason, only the preceding mode of EPSL is considered. Some alternatives to the continuous EPSL/NSL transition are discussed in Sect. 4.

2.3 Source distribution

With the simplification described in Sect. 2.4 the astrometric accuracy can be estimated for any number of sources, large or small. For the present analysis we need a number that is large enough to sample all the various parts of the sky, so that reliable statistics and visually pleasing maps can be produced, but nothing is gained by using many more sources. The results given below are always based on 12,288 sources placed in a healpix configuration (depth 5), yielding a mean density of about 0.3 sources per square degree.

2.4 Calculation of astrometric covariances

For the present analysis, based on the simplified model described above, the 5×5 covariance matrix of the astrometric parameters ($\alpha, \delta, \varpi, \mu_{\alpha*}, \mu_{\delta}$) is estimated as

$$C = \left(C_0^{-1} + \sum_k \mathbf{d}_k \mathbf{d}'_k \sigma_k^{-2} \right)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

¹In practice E will not exceed a few months, but values up to 6 are considered to illustrate the effect more clearly, and also because $E = 6$ gives a complete sky coverage in EPSL mode.

where the sum is taken over all along-scan astrometric (AF) observations k ,

$$\mathbf{d}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \eta_k}{\partial \alpha^*} \\ \frac{\partial \eta_k}{\partial \delta} \\ \frac{\partial \eta_k}{\partial \varpi} \\ \frac{\partial \eta_k}{\partial \mu_{\alpha^*}} \\ \frac{\partial \eta_k}{\partial \mu_{\delta}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

is the vector of the partial derivatives of the along-scan field angle η with respect to the five astrometric parameters, and \mathbf{C}_0 is the *a priori* covariance of the astrometric parameters (see below). A constant along-scan uncertainty $\sigma_k \equiv \sigma_{\text{AL}} = 141.4 \mu\text{as}$ is assumed, roughly corresponding to the bright-star performance in the absence of appreciable CTI effects, but including some attitude modelling and/or calibration errors. For the given scanning law and source parameters, the times of observation t_k are computed using the Scanner class in AGISLab, and the partial derivatives evaluated with the GenericFieldAngleCalculator in AGISTools. The summation and inversion of the symmetric (normal) matrix in Eq. (1) use the Normals class in GaiaTools. No dead time is assumed.

The *a priori* covariance \mathbf{C}_0 was introduced in order to cope with the cases when it is not possible to solve all five astrometric parameters for a given source, because there are not enough observations, or the observations have an unsuitable geometry or temporal distribution. This happens frequently in the early phases of the mission, especially during the first year. Without the *a priori* term in Eq. (1) the second term, obtained by summing over the observations, is then singular or nearly singular. In the real astrometric solution the action to be taken in such cases is to reduce the number of astrometric parameters to three (by discarding the proper motion components) or two (by discarding also the parallax); if the matrix is still singular, then no astrometric data can be obtained for this source. For the present analysis it is however not useful to compute formal uncertainties for less than five parameters, because the neglected proper motion and/or parallax represent huge modelling errors which are not included in the formal uncertainties. Moreover, it would be difficult to interpret the statistics of positional uncertainties across the sky if a different number of parameters were used in different parts of the sky. The inclusion of the *a priori* covariance allows an elegant and simple (Bayesian) solution to this problem: provided that \mathbf{C}_0 is positive definite, the resulting matrix in Eq. (1) is also positive definite, and its inverse gives formal uncertainties that include the effects of the neglected parameters in cases where not all five can be determined. For the present analysis we use an *a priori* covariance corresponding to uncertainties of 1 arcsec in position and parallax, and 1 arcsec yr⁻¹ for the proper motions. This means that the resulting uncertainties (σ_{α^*} , etc.) will never exceed these values – even if there are no Gaia observations. These *a priori* values are a bit on the high

side for most stars, but this is not really a problem if we are mainly analysing the *weights* of the astrometric data, proportional to $\sigma_{\alpha^*}^{-2}$ etc., since the *a priori* weight is completely negligible compared to even that of a single Gaia observation.

3 Results

In this Section we first present diagrams showing the *median* weights in position, parallax, and proper motion as functions of E and L . Median quantities are used because there is quite some variation across the sky, and we want to present the overall accuracies. Then, in Sect. 3.2, we illustrate how the uncertainties vary across the sky by giving some example maps for some selected combinations of E and L . Finally in Sect. 3.3 we give results for the 10th percentile instead of median values; this is in order to illustrate what happens in the 10% worst part of the sky.

3.1 Evolution of the median weights

Subsequent plots (Figs. 2–4) show the evolution of the median weights in position, parallax, and proper motion as functions of $L = E + N$, i.e., the total length of the science data acquisition phase. In each diagram, the different curves are for different lengths of the EPSL phase: $E = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 6$. More precisely, the plotted quantities are:

- the median weight per source in position, defined as $(0.1 \text{ mas}/\sigma_{\text{pos}})^2$, where σ_{pos} is the semi-major axis of the error ellipse in position at the effective epoch of observation;
- the median weight per source in parallax, defined as $(0.1 \text{ mas}/\sigma_{\text{par}})^2$, where σ_{par} is the standard uncertainty of the parallax;
- the median weight per source in proper motion, defined as $(0.1 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}/\sigma_{\text{pm}})^2$, where σ_{pm} is the semi-major axis of the error ellipse in proper motion.

The effective epoch of observation and the semi-major axis of the error ellipse are defined in Appendix A. As could be expected, the plots show that an increased time in EPSL mode invariably decreases the astrometric weight at any given point in the mission. For comparison, Fig. 5 shows the evolution of the median number of observations per source. Here, the curves for the different E almost coincide, which is to be expected since the mean number of observations per source is independent of the scanning law.

A simple way to quantify the astrometric impact of E months of EPSL is to find out how much *additional* time in NSL mode is needed to compensate for for the EPSL, i.e., to achieve the same

median weight in positions, parallaxes, or proper motions. Let $W(L, E)$ be the median weight obtained for a total observation time of L months including E months of EPSL (followed by $N = L - E$ months of NSL). Now define the 'compensation time' ΔN such that $W(L + \Delta N, E) = W(L, 0)$. Finally let us define the 'compensation factor' $F = \Delta N/E$. Clearly $F = 0$ means that $W(L, E) = W(L, 0)$, i.e., that the EPSL had no adverse effect of the astrometric weight after L months. On the other extreme, a compensation factor of $F = 1$ means that $W(L + E, E) = W(L, 0)$, i.e., that the EPSL was a complete waste of time from the point of view of the accumulated astrometric weight after L months. The ΔN can easily be read off the diagrams in Figs. 2–4 (or obtained by inverse interpolation in the tables used to produce the diagrams), from which F can be computed. The results are shown in Figs. 6–8.

It is seen that the compensation factor F is generally in the range from 0.6 to 1.0, and more typically around 0.8 or 0.9 for $L < 24$ months. This means that the EPSL is of little use for the astrometry, especially during the first few years of the mission.

FIGURE 2: Evolution of the median weight in position as a function of the total length of the observations. The different curves are for different lengths of the EP SL phase, as indicated by the legends. The lower diagram is a zoom-in on the first two years of the mission.

FIGURE 3: Same as Fig. 2 but for the parallaxes.

FIGURE 4: Same as Fig. 2 but for the proper motions.

FIGURE 5: Evolution of the median number of observations per source.

FIGURE 6: The compensation factor $F = \Delta N/E$ for the median weight in position as a function of the total length of the observations. Here, ΔN is the additional time in NSL mode needed to compensate for the initial E months of EPSL. The different curves are for different E , as indicated by the legends.

FIGURE 7: Same as Fig. 6 but for the parallaxes.

FIGURE 8: Same as Fig. 6 but for the proper motions.

3.2 Sample maps

The EPSL not only increases the overall astrometric uncertainties, as illustrated in by the median values in the previous section, but it also makes the sky coverage more inhomogeneous. This is best illustrated by maps showing the uncertainty as a function of the position on the celestial sphere for specific combinations of L and E . Only a few selected examples are given here. The colour coding uses a logarithmic scale ranging from $10 \mu\text{as} (\text{yr}^{-1})$ to $30\text{--}1000 \mu\text{as} (\text{yr}^{-1})$ depending L and the quantity considered. Since the uncertainties were calculated for one source at the centre of each healpix cell, the maps show their variations across the sky at a resolution of about 2° . Given the colour coding covering a wide range of uncertainties, changes by 10 or even 20% are often quite invisible in these maps, although they might be scientifically quite important.

Figure 9 shows the positional uncertainty, σ_{pos} (defined as in Sect. 3.1) and the parallax uncertainty, σ_{par} for $L = 12$ months of mission data, including $E = 0, 1, 2,$ and 3 months of EPSL. Figure 10 shows a similar set of maps for the uncertainty in proper motion and the number of astrometric (AF, AL) observations per source.

The corresponding maps for $L = 18$ months are shown in Figs. 11–12, and for $L = 24$ months in Figs. 13–14.

FIGURE 9: Standard uncertainties of positions (left) and parallaxes (right) for $L = 12$ months of mission data. From top to bottom, the EP SL lasts for $E = 0, 1, 2,$ and 3 months.

FIGURE 10: Same as Fig. 9 but for the standard uncertainties of proper motions (left) and the number of along-scan AF observations (right).

FIGURE 11: Standard uncertainties of positions (left) and parallaxes (right) for $L = 18$ months of mission data. From top to bottom, the EPSL lasts for $E = 0, 1, 2,$ and 3 months.

FIGURE 12: Same as Fig. 11 but for the standard uncertainties of proper motions (left) and the number of along-scan AF observations (right).

FIGURE 13: Standard uncertainties of positions (left) and parallaxes (right) for $L = 24$ months of mission data. From top to bottom, the EPSL lasts for $E = 0, 1, 2,$ and 3 months.

FIGURE 14: Same as Fig. 13 but for the standard uncertainties of proper motions (left) and the number of along-scan AF observations (right).

3.3 Evolution of the 10th percentile of the weights

As illustrated by the sample maps, the impact of the EPSL is very different depending on the position on the sky. This means that some parts of the sky are much more degraded than suggested by the median values in Sect. 3.1, while other parts are hardly affected at all. One way to quantify this effect is to consider some other (lower) percentile of the weights instead of the median (= 50th percentile). As an example, Figs. 15–17 show the evolution of the 10th percentile of the weights in position, parallax, and proper motion. The plots show that the ‘worst’ parts of the sky (quantified by the 10th percentile in weight) need a similar amount of compensation time in NSL as the median sky, or even slightly more: the compensation factors (Figs. 18–20) are consistently higher than for the median (cf. Tables 1 and 2).²

²The values of F shown in Figs. 18–20 sometimes exceed 1 which may at first seem odd, since it means that the missing E months of NSL at the beginning of the mission require more than E months of NSL in compensation. However, the compensational NSL occurs at a different time, and therefore does not necessarily help the sources that were missed during the EPSL phase, depending on where in the mission we look (L). Hence the rather strong oscillations in these diagrams. In the long run they average out, and the mean values in Table 2 are therefore probably more representative.

FIGURE 15: Evolution of the 10th percentile of the weight in position as a function of the total length of the observations. The different curves are for different lengths of the EP SL phase, as indicated by the legends. The lower diagram is a zoom-in on the first two years.

FIGURE 16: Same as Fig. 15 but for the parallaxes.

FIGURE 17: Same as Fig. 15 but for the proper motions.

FIGURE 18: The compensation factor $F = \Delta N/E$ for the 10th percentile weight in position as a function of the total length of the observations. Here, ΔN is the additional time in NSL mode needed to compensate for the initial E months of EPSL. The different curves are for different E , as indicated by the legends.

FIGURE 19: Same as Fig. 18 but for the parallaxes.

FIGURE 20: Same as Fig. 18 but for the proper motions.

TABLE 1: Average compensation factor F applicable to the median weights in position, parallax, and proper motion. The meaning of F is that E months of EPSL require an additional **FE months** of compensational time in NSL to reach the same overall accuracy, as measured by the median weights.

$\Delta\nu =$	0°	90°	180°	270°
Position	0.83	0.86	0.82	0.87
Parallax	0.78	0.72	0.75	0.81
Proper motion	0.85	0.86	0.85	0.85

TABLE 2: Same as Table 1 but for the 10th percentile of the weights in position, parallax, and proper motion.

$\Delta\nu =$	0°	90°	180°	270°
Position	0.93	0.90	0.93	0.91
Parallax	0.86	0.84	0.81	0.85
Proper motion	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.86

4 Alternative scanning patterns

For all the results reported above, the NSL is assumed to follow the EPSL without a gap in the motion of the spin (z) axis. That is, since the EPSL is made in the preceding mode (with constant $\nu = 0$), the NSL starts with $\nu(t_{\text{switch}}) = 0$ at the switch-over time. It can be argued that the NSL would be able to **'catch up'** more quickly if it started at some other value of ν , causing a gap in the motion of the z axis at switch-over.³ The resulting astrometric accuracy can be analysed as a function of L and E exactly as in Sect. 3 for different amounts of the step $\Delta\nu$ in the ν angle. However, rather than presenting a whole new bunch of diagrams for different values of $\Delta\nu$, we give in Table 1 just the average value of the compensation factor F over the range $L = 9$ to 51 months. The corresponding average compensation factors for the 10th percentile weights are shown in Table 2.

Only three different values of $\Delta\nu$ have been investigated in addition to the default $\Delta\nu = 0$. However, none of them gives any significant improvement (in terms of a smaller F) over the default value. Hence we conclude that it is not likely that the negative impact of the EPSL can be mitigated by using a non-**negative** $\Delta\nu$.

³Such a switch-over manoeuvre would not be instantaneous, but would necessarily give some additional dead-time. This complication is however ignored for the sake of the present study.

5 Discussion and conclusion

From the simulations presented above it is clear that the EPSL mode is of very limited use for astrometry, and that the time in EPSL should therefore be minimised. Roughly speaking, for every month of science time spent in EPSL, one would need to add 3 to 4 weeks in NSL mode to reach the same overall sky coverage and accuracy as without the EPSL. This rule of thumb is applicable to any duration of the EPSL mode, and throughout the mission – the initial loss in EPSL mode is never ‘caught up’ by the NSL, except by this extra (compensation) time in NSL mode. At the end of a nominal five-year mission, the global loss in terms of the astrometric weight is about 1–1.5% per month of EPSL for the positions and parallaxes, and about 4–4.5% for the proper motions. The EPSL also introduces an increased non-uniformity of the sky coverage, as illustrated by the sample maps in Sect. 3.2.

The overall conclusion from this study is therefore that the EPSL mode should not be used beyond what is strictly necessary for the commissioning and initial in-orbit calibration. This conclusion is amplified by considerations of risk and hardware performance:

1. Although the overall effect of the time in EPSL mode is rather small at the end of a five-year mission, it is relatively much bigger earlier in the mission. When assessing the impact of the EPSL one must factor in the risk that the mission ends prematurely, or is severely damaged by a major solar eruption in the early part of the mission. In such a case the relative loss in astrometric weight due to an extended EPSL phase could be dramatic.
2. The performance degradation of the CCDs due to the accumulated radiation damage will start immediately after launch. The first months of science data acquisition are therefore in a certain sense more valuable than the same amount of time later in the mission, and it therefore seems particularly wasteful to spend an extended time in EPSL during this part of the mission.

The negative impact of the EPSL addressed here must of course be weighed against the possibility to improve and/or accelerate the calibration of for example CTI in EPSL mode, which will indirectly benefit the astrometry. However, there are good reasons to think that any such calibration can be achieved just as well (and quite possibly better) in NSL mode, although it will take longer and require a more complex analysis of a larger data set. Scientifically, the need for an early and precise calibration is clearly justified, e.g., by the science alert. This is therefore one of the science issues that must be weighed against the overall astrometric loss discussed above, including the risk of an early end to the mission.

The simulations described here are based on highly idealised assumptions, in particular that there is no dead time and that the attitude determination and instrument calibration in all cases can be achieved to sufficient accuracy. An interesting question is what would happen under more realistic assumptions. To address this question it is really necessary to make a much more

detailed simulation, including a realistic attitude, dead time, and a full AGIS solution with at least several million primary sources. This was not feasible in the framework of the present study. Theoretically, however, we do not expect that the general picture would change much, since to a first approximation the attitude determination and calibration both in EPSL and NSL are similarly affected by data gaps, high-frequency attitude noise and most other effects. If anything, one should expect the dead time and data gaps to make the early solutions (i.e., for small L) more fragile to deviations from the NSL.

A Appendix: Some mathematical details

A.1 The mean epoch of observation

The astrometric weight in position depends strongly on the epoch considered, with a global maximum near the mean epoch of observation. For a regular scanning pattern such as NSL, and assuming that the observational uncertainty is roughly constant (for a given magnitude), the mean epoch of observation is usually quite close to mid-mission. Therefore, the positional uncertainties σ_{α^*} and σ_{δ} are usually calculated for a source reference epoch exactly mid-mission (e.g., J2016.5 for a five-year mission starting at J2014.0), where the uncertainties are close to their minimum values.

When the weight and distribution of observations vary a lot throughout the mission, and also in the present case when EPSL and NSL are combined, the optimum epoch for the positions is not necessarily close to mid-mission, and the usual recipe, outlined above, would give slightly misleading values, especially when comparing different scanning laws for which the optimum epochs might differ. In order to avoid arbitrariness, it is expedient to calculate the optimum epoch more precisely by minimising the positional uncertainties. This can be done quite easily, given the 5×5 covariance matrix of the astrometric parameters referred to an arbitrary reference epoch, e.g., at the beginning of the mission. The required formulae are given in Sects. 1.2.7 and 1.5.4 of ESA (1997), Vol 1, and are only repeated here for convenience. Let

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{00} & C_{01} & \cdots & C_{04} \\ C_{10} & C_{11} & \cdots & C_{14} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{40} & C_{41} & \cdots & C_{44} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

be the original covariance matrix referring to the reference epoch t_{ref} . Shifting to the new epoch $t_{\text{ref}} + t$ gives the modified covariance

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{C}\mathbf{J}', \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the Jacobian

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & t & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The effective epoch of observation is obtained by minimising the trace of the covariance matrix

$$\text{tr}(\hat{\mathbf{C}}) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}) + 2(C_{03} + C_{14})t + (C_{33} + C_{44})t^2, \quad (6)$$

with the result

$$t = -\frac{C_{03} + C_{14}}{C_{33} + C_{44}}, \quad (7)$$

FIGURE 21: Illustrating the relation between the error ellipse in two dimensions (here called x and y) and the one-dimensional uncertainty. The red curve is the error ellipse for the case $\sigma_x = 1$, $\sigma_y = 2$, $\rho = 0.8$. For a bivariate Gaussian distribution, the error ellipse is an isodensity curve for the joint probability density of (x, y) . The blue curve is a polar plot of σ_θ , the uncertainty in direction θ , calculated according to Eq. (9). Note that the two curves touch each other at the apses, and that σ_θ has a very narrow minimum for a direction along the minor axis of the error ellipse. The solid black lines are $\pm 1\sigma$ error bars along the x and y axes, and the dashed rectangle is the corresponding one-sigma ‘error box’, which is tangent to the error ellipse.

cf. Eq. [1.2.10] in ESA (1997). Since the trace of a square matrix is invariant with respect to an orthogonal transformation, this result is independent of the coordinate system used.

For the present simulations the effective epoch, as defined above, has been used throughout to calculate the weight in position. A slight complication is that the prior covariance \mathbf{C}_0 in Eq. (1) ideally should use the same effective epoch, which however can only be calculated after the normal matrix (including the prior) has been inverted. The pragmatic solution is to use a provisional reference epoch, half-way through the NSL phase (i.e., $t_{\text{beg}} + E + N/2$), to evaluate Eq. (1), after which a correction to the effective epoch is computed as described above. The fact that the prior covariance may refer to a slightly ‘wrong’ epoch will have negligible impact on the results.

A.2 The semi-major axis of the error ellipse

The uncertainty in position is a two-dimensional quantity which in general requires at least three numbers for its characterisation, e.g., the standard deviations σ_{α^*} and σ_{δ} along two orthogonal axes plus a correlation coefficient $\rho_{\alpha^*\delta}$. Equivalently, we may use the 2×2 covariance matrix with elements $C_{00} = \sigma_{\alpha^*}^2$, $C_{11} = \sigma_{\delta}^2$, and $C_{01} = C_{10} = \rho_{\alpha^*\delta}\sigma_{\alpha^*}\sigma_{\delta}$. Graphically, the uncertainty can be represented by an ellipse whose dimensions and orientation can be computed from these numbers (cf. Fig. 21). The uncertainty in proper motion can be characterised correspondingly.

For many purposes it is useful to have a *single* number to quantify the uncertainty in position (or proper motion). Neither σ_{α^*} nor σ_{δ} is suitable, because the choice between them would be arbitrary, and both depend on the (again arbitrary) choice of equatorial coordinates rather than, for example, galactic coordinates. In the previous section we already encountered a quantity which is invariant with respect to the choice of coordinate system, namely the trace of the covariance matrix, or $\sigma_{\alpha^*}^2 + \sigma_{\delta}^2$ (which is minimised at the effective epoch). As will be shown below, this quantity equals twice the positional variance averaged over all position angles. Thus, a rather natural choice for the positional uncertainty is the root-mean-square (RMS) average with respect to direction,

$$\sigma_{\text{pos,rms}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{\alpha^*}^2 + \sigma_{\delta}^2}{2}}. \quad (8)$$

This is a good choice especially if the error ellipse is not very elongated.

In the present simulations it may however happen that the error ellipse is quite elongated because of the EPSL, which in the ecliptic region allows the ecliptic latitude to be determined much more accurately than the longitude. In such cases the RMS positional error could be misleading, because very few scientific applications could benefit from the high accuracy achieved in some very particular direction (e.g., ecliptic latitude), if the uncertainty is much larger in other directions. The semi-major axis of the error ellipse may then be a more appropriate measure of the positional uncertainty.

The quantities σ_{α^*} and σ_{δ} are the positional uncertainties (at the given epoch) along a direction in position angle $\theta = 90^\circ$ (or 270°) and 0° (or 180°), respectively. More generally, the variance in position along the arbitrary position angle θ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\theta}^2 &= \sigma_{\alpha^*}^2 \sin^2 \theta + \sigma_{\delta}^2 \cos^2 \theta + 2\rho_{\alpha\delta}\sigma_{\alpha^*}\sigma_{\delta} \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(C_{00} + C_{11}) + \frac{1}{2}(C_{11} - C_{00}) \cos 2\theta + C_{01} \sin 2\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The one-dimensional uncertainty σ_{θ} , when plotted in a polar diagram, is not an error ellipse, however; in general it is an elongated figure (the blue curve in Fig. 21) with a more or less pronounced waistline along the minor axis of the error ellipse (the red curve in Fig. 21). σ_{θ} therefore has a minimum in the direction of the minor axis, but in nearly any other direction the one-dimensional uncertainty is dominated by the projection of the larger error along the major

axis. From Eq. (9) it is readily seen that averaging σ_θ^2 with respect to θ gives the RMS value in Eq. (8).

The directions for the extreme values of σ_θ can be obtained by solving the equation for the stationary points, $d\sigma_\theta^2/d\theta = 0$; the result is

$$\tan 2\theta = \frac{2C_{01}}{C_{11} - C_{00}}. \quad (10)$$

The corresponding minimum and maximum variances are

$$[\sigma_\theta^2]_{\min, \max} = \frac{1}{2}(C_{00} + C_{11}) \pm \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{(C_{11} - C_{00})^2 + 4C_{01}^2}. \quad (11)$$

On the other hand, the semi-minor and semi-major axes (squared) of the error ellipse are obtained by solving the eigenvalue equation,

$$\begin{vmatrix} C_{00} - \lambda & C_{01} \\ C_{10} & C_{11} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (12)$$

The roots of this quadratic equation are exactly Eq. (11), which shows that the extreme values of σ_θ equal the semi-axes of the error ellipse. For the present study we adopt the maximum one-dimensional uncertainty

$$\sigma_{\text{pos}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(C_{00} + C_{11}) + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{(C_{11} - C_{00})^2 + 4C_{01}^2}} \quad (13)$$

as a measure of the positional uncertainty. As shown above, this quantity can also be interpreted as the semi-major axis of the error ellipse. Correspondingly for the proper motions we define

$$\sigma_{\text{pm}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(C_{33} + C_{44}) + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{(C_{44} - C_{33})^2 + 4C_{34}^2}}. \quad (14)$$

Given that the above definition of the positional uncertainty, it would be natural to define the effective epoch in terms of minimising σ_{pos} rather than $\sigma_{\text{pos,rms}}$, as was done in Appendix A.1. Unfortunately, minimising the semi-major axis turns out to be rather more complicated – it leads to an algebraic equation of degree six –, and the simpler approach of Appendix A.1 was therefore adopted.

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